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A screen to identify genes that confer resistance to doxorubicin.

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Medical oncology demands use of precision medicine to challenge resistance to clinical intervention. Doxorubicin resistance is a clinical problem for solid tumor patients whose regimens include use of the anthracycline including breast cancer and osteosarcoma. We conducted an expression screen to identify genes important for resistance to doxorubicin in cancer cells. We describe here some conserved changes shared between systems that model doxorubicin resistance in patients with cancer including silencing or activation of HOX locus non-coding RNAs HOTAIR and HOTAIRM1, respectively, activation of ICAM2, and apparent silencing of growth regulation by estrogen in breast cancer 1 *GREB1* or *GREB1L*.